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Agency Banking And Its Effects On Income Generation And Poverty Reduction In Katsina State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the impact of agency banking on income generation and poverty reduction in Katsina State, Nigeria, against the backdrop of persistent unemployment, low income, and limited access to formal financial services. Using primary data collected through structured questionnaires administered to 358 agency banking operators across different communities in the state, the study adopts both descriptive statistics and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to analyze the relationships between agency banking activities and income-related outcomes. The findings reveal that agency banking plays a significant role in generating income and employment opportunities, particularly through transaction-based services such as cash withdrawals, deposits, and fund transfers. These services constitute the main sources of agents' earnings and contribute to improved household welfare. The results further show that income generation through agency banking is largely inclusive, as it is not significantly influenced by gender or high levels of formal education. Based on the empirical evidence, the study recommends the expansion of agency banking networks, especially in rural and underserved areas, through wider geographic coverage, simplified onboarding procedures, and the provision of start-up capital. Continuous capacity building, performance-based incentives, and financial management training are also recommended to enhance agents' productivity and earnings. Finally, the study recommends that financial institutions provide low-interest, flexible loan products to support asset acquisition, business expansion, and long-term income stability, thereby reinforcing the role of agency banking as a sustainable tool for poverty reduction in Katsina State.

Keywords: Agency Banking, Income, Cash Withdrawal, Cash Deposit, Poverty Reduction

1. INTRODUCTION

Unemployment and low income remain among the most persistent development challenges globally, despite decades of policy interventions aimed at promoting inclusive economic growth. More than 200 million people worldwide are currently unemployed, while millions of others are engaged in unstable, low-productivity activities that generate insufficient income to lift households out of poverty (ILO, 2023). In many developing economies, the problem is not only the absence of jobs but also the prevalence of poorly remunerated livelihoods that fail to provide economic security or upward mobility. Although some progress has been recorded in parts of Asia and Latin America where financial inclusion, digital finance,

and small enterprise development have expanded income-generating opportunities regions such as South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa continue to experience widespread labour market distress and persistent income poverty (UNDP, 2022).

In countries such as India and Bangladesh, development strategies have increasingly shifted from charity-based interventions to financial empowerment approaches that emphasize income generation and self-employment. Through microfinance, mobile banking, and digital payment systems, households have been able to establish small businesses, smooth consumption, build assets, and reduce vulnerability to poverty (Kabeer, 2019). These experiences underscore the role of inclusive financial systems in transforming employment into sustainable income streams rather than temporary survival activities.

In Africa, unemployment and poverty are more complex and multidimensional. Beyond job scarcity, the challenge is characterized by limited access to productive capital, low skills acquisition, irregular and unstable incomes, weak access to education and healthcare, and high exposure to economic shocks (UNDP, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic, political instability, and climate-related disruptions have further weakened livelihoods across Sub-Saharan Africa, eroding incomes and pushing many households back into poverty despite earlier development gains (World Bank, 2022). Consequently, income generation has become as critical a policy concern as employment creation itself.

Nigeria, despite being Africa's largest economy with abundant human and natural resources, continues to grapple with high unemployment, underemployment, and widespread income poverty. Since independence, successive governments have implemented several employment and poverty-alleviation programmes such as NAPEP, NSIP, GEEP, and the Anchor Borrowers' Programme but their impacts have often been inconsistent, short-lived, and insufficient to generate sustainable income growth (Isana & Ademeso, 2025). The removal of fuel subsidies in 2023 further intensified economic hardship by increasing production and transportation costs, weakening small businesses, reducing real incomes, and worsening household welfare. As of 2024, over 40 percent of Nigeria's labour force is either unemployed or underemployed, with youth unemployment and working poverty at particularly alarming levels (NBS, 2024).

Katsina State exemplifies one of the most severe employment and income challenges in Nigeria. With a rapidly growing population, limited industrial activity, and weak formal-sector absorption capacity, many residents depend on informal, low-income, and highly unstable economic activities. Households often experience low earnings, poor access to healthcare and education, food insecurity, and limited ownership of productive assets. Importantly, these conditions persist not because of a lack of willingness to work, but due to structural constraints such as poor access to financial services, inadequate business capital, and weak market linkages that restrict residents' ability to engage in profitable income-generating activities (NBS, 2024).

Against this backdrop, financial inclusion particularly through agency banking has emerged as a promising pathway for employment creation, income generation, and poverty reduction. Agency banking involves the appointment of individuals or small businesses as authorized agents to provide basic financial services such as cash deposits and withdrawals, fund transfers, bill payments, and, in some cases, access to microcredit and insurance products (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017; EFINA, 2020). By lowering the cost and distance barriers associated with conventional banking, agency banking brings financial services closer to underserved communities, enabling households and micro-entrepreneurs to save, transact, invest, and manage risks more effectively.

For agents themselves, agency banking offers direct self-employment opportunities and a steady source of income through commissions and service charges. It also supports entrepreneurship, promotes income diversification, enhances financial discipline, facilitates asset accumulation, and strengthens household resilience against economic shocks (Ikram & Lodhi, 2015; Cumming et al., 2014). Beyond the agents, agency banking stimulates local economic activity by easing transactions for traders, farmers, and small businesses, thereby indirectly supporting income growth and poverty reduction within communities. In this sense, agency banking functions not merely as a financial service delivery channel but as a livelihood strategy with the potential to expand income-earning opportunities at the grassroots level.

However, despite its rapid expansion, the actual impact of agency banking on income generation and poverty reduction in Katsina State remains insufficiently understood. While conventional government employment programmes have struggled to produce lasting outcomes, agency banking has increasingly become a preferred livelihood option for many youths and women. Yet critical questions persist: Does agency banking generate reliable and sustainable income capable of lifting households out of poverty? Does participation in agency banking improve access to essential needs such as healthcare, education, food security, and asset ownership? Or does it merely provide marginal earnings within a highly competitive and low-margin digital finance ecosystem?

This knowledge gap is particularly significant for Katsina State, where thousands of individuals have adopted agency banking as an alternative to scarce formal employment opportunities. In the absence of empirical evidence, policymakers and development practitioners cannot determine whether agency banking should be scaled up as a core income and poverty-reduction strategy or treated solely as a supplementary financial inclusion tool. Consequently, this study investigates the impact of agency banking on income generation and poverty reduction in Katsina State. Specifically, it examines how engagement in agency banking influences agents' income levels, employment creation, skill development, household welfare, asset accumulation, and overall poverty status. By providing empirical insights into these dimensions, the study offers evidence-based guidance for positioning agency banking as a viable instrument for inclusive growth, sustainable livelihoods, and poverty reduction in Katsina State and Nigeria at large.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Literature

Agency banking refers to the provision of basic financial services through third-party agents who operate on behalf of licensed financial institutions. These services include cash deposits and withdrawals, fund transfers, bill payments, account opening facilitation, and, in some cases, access to microcredit and micro-insurance products (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017; EFINA, 2020). Typically, agents are small-scale entrepreneurs such as retail shop owners, mobile money operators, and POS merchants who leverage their proximity to local communities to extend banking services to underserved populations.

In contexts like Katsina State where conventional banking infrastructure is limited and rural settlements dominate agency banking plays a critical role in bridging the gap between formal financial institutions and excluded households. By reducing distance, documentation, and transaction costs, agency banking lowers barriers to entry into the formal financial system, thereby enhancing financial inclusion and stimulating income-generating activities (Nwankwo & Eze, 2019). The expansion of agency banking is therefore closely linked to improved livelihood opportunities, especially for individuals who previously relied on informal and unstable economic activities.

Employment generation, on the other hand, refers to the creation of opportunities that enable individuals to engage in productive activities that yield income, enhance welfare, and reduce vulnerability to poverty (ILO, 2021). Employment may be formal or informal and may arise through wage labour, self-employment, entrepreneurship, or business expansion. In the context of agency banking, employment generation is particularly associated with self-employment and micro-entrepreneurship, as individuals operate POS outlets and mobile money businesses as primary or supplementary sources of income.

Agency banking contributes to employment and income generation through three interrelated channels. First, direct employment occurs when individuals become agents or POS operators, creating self-employment opportunities and earning commissions that improve household income. Second, indirect employment arises as agency banking stimulates local commerce by facilitating transactions for traders, farmers, and small businesses, thereby supporting ancillary services such as transportation, retail supply, and logistics. Third, induced employment emerges as increased income among agents and users boosts local consumption, which in turn generates additional economic activities within the community. Through these channels, agency banking functions as both a financial inclusion strategy and a local economic empowerment mechanism.

2.2 Theoretical Literature

Financial Intermediation Theory

The Financial Intermediation Theory, originally advanced by Gurley and Shaw (1960), provides a relevant theoretical foundation for understanding the role of agency banking in income generation and poverty reduction. The theory posits that financial intermediaries play a central role in mobilizing savings, reducing transaction costs, managing risk, and allocating financial resources efficiently within an economy. By doing so, intermediaries promote investment, economic activity, and employment.

In the context of agency banking, financial intermediation is enhanced through the decentralization of banking services to community-based agents. Rather than relying solely on costly brick-and-mortar branches, banks outsource low-value and high-volume transactions to agents who operate at significantly lower costs. This arrangement improves operational efficiency, widens financial outreach, and increases access to financial services among low-income populations. Importantly, the theory suggests that as financial intermediation becomes more inclusive, economic participation expands, leading to job creation and income growth.

Applied to Katsina State, Financial Intermediation Theory implies that agency banking can simultaneously strengthen financial sector efficiency and create employment opportunities at the grassroots level. By enabling agents to earn income through commissions and facilitating access to capital for micro-entrepreneurs, agency banking supports productive engagement, asset accumulation, and poverty reduction. Thus, financial intermediaries not only promote financial deepening but also act as catalysts for inclusive employment and income generation.

2.3 Empirical Literature

Empirical studies conducted within Nigeria provide mixed but generally supportive evidence regarding the role of agency banking in improving income and reducing poverty. Studies in states such as Benue, Plateau, and Katsina (Jabir & Saminu, 2024; Ajam, 2023; Akighir et al., 2020; Akintunde et al., 2024) report that agency banking enhances financial accessibility, reduces transaction costs, and improves income levels for agents and small business operators. These studies highlight the importance of proximity and convenience in expanding financial usage among previously excluded populations.

However, despite these positive outcomes, several challenges persist. Security risks, low financial literacy, technological failures, liquidity constraints, and limited rural penetration continue to undermine the effectiveness of agency banking in Nigeria. Some studies (e.g., Nwachukwu et al., 2019) report weak or statistically insignificant relationships between agency banking or mobile money operations and financial inclusion, suggesting that contextual factors such as infrastructure quality and regulatory enforcement significantly influence outcomes.

Evidence from other African countries similarly reveals varied impacts. Studies from Tanzania, Uganda, Kenya, and Zimbabwe (Mbogo & Muturi, 2021; Charles & Mercerina, 2024; Asif, 2016; Munoru, 2016; Ansaful, 2019) generally find that agency banking expands outreach and improves access to basic financial services, particularly in underserved regions. Nonetheless, issues such as administrative bottlenecks, agent liquidity shortages, and infrastructural deficiencies often limit the income-generating potential of agency banking. In Kenya, for example, some studies observe that agency banking does not always translate into meaningful improvements in financial inclusion or income levels, underscoring the need for supportive regulatory and capacity-building frameworks.

Beyond agency banking, a broader strand of empirical literature examines financial inclusion and financial development as pathways to poverty reduction. Cross-country and country-specific studies across Africa, Asia, Latin America, and Europe consistently show that improved access to finance enhances household welfare, supports income generation, reduces poverty, and promotes economic development (Kumar & Jie, 2023; Saha & Qin, 2023; Lee et al., 2023; Dorothy et al., 2023). These studies demonstrate that financial access enables productive investment, consumption smoothing, and resilience to economic shocks. Some findings further reveal gender, regional, and income-based differences, with women and rural households often benefiting disproportionately from inclusive financial systems.

Panel and cross-country analyses (Omar & Inaba, 2020; Ouechtati, 2020; Appiah et al., 2020; Churchill & Marisetty, 2020) provide robust evidence that financial inclusion and financial development reduce poverty and income inequality over time, although the magnitude of effects varies across income groups and stages of development. Nevertheless, some scholars caution that rapid digital financial expansion may exacerbate inequality if not complemented by adequate regulation, financial literacy, and social protection policies.

Overall, the empirical literature affirms the relevance of agency banking and financial inclusion as tools for poverty reduction and income generation. However, variations in findings particularly within Nigeria and across African contexts reflect differences in institutional quality, infrastructure, methodology, and regional characteristics. These inconsistencies reinforce the need for localized empirical investigations.

2.4 Gaps Identified in the Existing Literature

Despite the growing body of literature on agency banking and financial inclusion, several critical gaps remain. First, most existing studies emphasize the relationship between financial inclusion and poverty reduction, with limited focus on employment and income generation, particularly in northern Nigeria and Katsina State. Second, many studies rely on descriptive or qualitative approaches, offering limited causal evidence on the income and welfare effects of agency banking. Third, prior research predominantly examines customers' access to financial services, while largely overlooking the socioeconomic outcomes for bank agents themselves.

Moreover, existing studies rarely consider multidimensional welfare indicators such as income stability, education, healthcare access, asset ownership, and household resilience. These gaps are particularly significant in regions like Katsina State, where agency banking has emerged as an alternative livelihood strategy amid persistent unemployment and poverty. Addressing these gaps, the present study provides a context-specific empirical analysis of the impact of agency banking on income generation, employment creation, and poverty reduction in Katsina State, thereby contributing to policy-relevant evidence for inclusive economic development in Nigeria.

3. METHODOLOGY

Following the conceptual, theoretical, and empirical discussions in the preceding chapter which highlighted the need for context-specific evidence on the income and employment effects of agency banking this chapter outlines the methodological approach adopted to address the identified research gaps. The methodology is structured to provide a rigorous and systematic examination of the impact of agency banking on income generation and employment outcomes in Katsina State, Nigeria. Specifically, the chapter discusses the research design, population of the study, sample size and sampling technique, sources and instruments of data collection, and methods of data analysis.

3.1 Research Design

The study adopts a cross-sectional survey research design, which involves collecting data from respondents at a single point in time. This design is appropriate for the present study because it allows for the empirical assessment of relationships between agency banking operations and employment-related outcomes, including income generation, job creation, and welfare indicators. Given the dynamic and rapidly expanding nature of agency banking in Katsina State, a cross-sectional approach provides a cost-effective and timely means of capturing current operational realities and socioeconomic effects among agency banking operators and workers. Moreover, the design is well suited for examining patterns, associations, and structural relationships between variables, consistent with the study's analytical framework

3.2 Population of the Study

The population of the study consists of all individuals and outlets directly engaged in agency banking activities in Katsina State. This includes registered POS operators and authorized agents operating on behalf of licensed financial institutions. According to records from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2023), there are approximately 2,596 registered agency banking outlets across the state. These outlets constitute the primary units of analysis, as they represent the core platforms through which agency

banking contributes to employment creation, income generation, and local economic activity. Focusing on this population ensures that the study captures first-hand evidence on the employment and welfare outcomes associated with agency banking operations.

3.3 Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A sample size of 358 respondents was determined using Yamane’s (1967) sample size determination formula, which provides a simplified and statistically reliable method for estimating sample sizes for finite populations at a 95 percent confidence level and a 5 percent margin of error. This sample size is considered adequate to generate robust and generalizable findings for the study population.

To ensure adequate representation and reduce sampling bias, the study employs a stratified random sampling technique. The population was first stratified based on local government areas (LGAs) within Katsina State to account for geographic diversity and variations in agency banking density. Subsequently, respondents were randomly selected from each stratum in proportion to the number of agency banking outlets operating in each LGA. This approach enhances the representativeness of the sample and ensures that both urban and rural agency banking experiences are adequately captured.

3.4 Methods of Data Analysis

Data collected from the field were analyzed using a combination of descriptive and inferential statistical techniques, with particular emphasis on Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Descriptive statistics including frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations were employed to summarize respondents’ demographic characteristics, operational features of agency banking, and employment-related outcomes. These statistics provide a clear overview of the distributional patterns and basic characteristics of agency banking operations in Katsina State.

For inferential analysis, Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) was utilized to examine the complex relationships between agency banking and employment outcomes. SEM is particularly suitable for this study because it enables the simultaneous estimation of multiple relationships and the incorporation of latent constructs such as *Agency Banking Effectiveness*, *Income Generation*, and *Employment Creation*, which are measured through several observed indicators. Additionally, SEM allows for the assessment of both direct and indirect effects, thereby capturing the pathways through which agency banking influences employment and income outcomes. The use of SEM enhances the robustness, validity, and explanatory power of the empirical analysis and aligns with the multidimensional nature of employment and welfare outcomes identified in the literature.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This subsection presents the results of the path coefficients derived from the PLS-SEM analysis. The results of the PLS-SEM analysis, presented in Table 4.1, reveal the relative influence of different agency banking services and demographic factors on employment creation. The path coefficients (β), t-statistics, and p-values provide insights into which factors significantly drive job opportunities within agency banking operations in Katsina State.

Table 4.1: Results of Path Coefficients for Model 2:- Income Generation

Models	Coefficients (β)	Standard error	T statistics	P values
Account Opening	0.116	0.062	1.871	0.063
Cash Deposit	0.307	0.044	6.977	0.000
Cash withdrawal	0.594	0.060	9.900	0.000
Transfers	0.230	0.052	4.423	0.000
Payment of utilities	0.134	0.045	2.978	0.003
Educational Qualification	0.071	0.039	1.821	0.071
Gender	0.041	0.036	1.139	0.261
Constant	0.312	0.081	3.852	0.000

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025), using Smart PLS_4 Version 4.1.1.4

The results in Table 4.1 reveal that agency banking services significantly influence income generation, thereby validating the central argument advanced in the background and conceptual literature that agency banking functions not merely as a financial inclusion tool but also as a viable livelihood and income-generating strategy in contexts characterized by limited formal employment opportunities, such as Katsina State.

Consistent with expectations and earlier empirical evidence, cash withdrawal services emerge as the strongest determinant of income generation among agency banking operators ($\beta = 0.594$, $p < 0.01$). This result reflects the transaction-intensive nature of withdrawals in rural and semi-urban settings where cash-based economic activities dominate. As noted in the conceptual discussion, high transaction frequency directly translates into higher commission earnings for agents. This finding aligns with Financial Intermediation Theory (Gurley & Shaw, 1960), which emphasizes the role of intermediaries in reducing transaction costs and facilitating liquidity circulation within the economy. Empirically, the result corroborates studies by Akighir et al. (2020), Ajam (2023), and Jabir and Saminu (2024), which similarly identified cash withdrawals as the primary income driver for POS operators in northern Nigeria.

Cash deposit services also exert a strong and statistically significant positive effect on income generation ($\beta = 0.307$, $p < 0.01$). This finding underscores the growing reliance of small traders, farmers, and salary earners on agency banking outlets for safe and convenient savings services. As highlighted in the earlier empirical literature, deposit mobilization enhances agents' earnings while simultaneously deepening financial inclusion (Demirguc-Kunt et al., 2017). In Katsina State, where access to conventional bank branches is limited, the role of agents as localized financial intermediaries significantly boosts their income-generating capacity.

Similarly, fund transfers have a positive and significant effect on income generation ($\beta = 0.230$, $p < 0.01$). This result reflects increased inter-household remittances, business transactions, and social transfers facilitated through agency banking channels. The finding reinforces earlier arguments that digital financial services expand market linkages and income opportunities for micro-entrepreneurs (EFInA, 2020; Nwankwo & Eze, 2019). It also supports cross-country evidence from Kenya and Tanzania, where transfers constitute a major revenue source for agents (Mbogo & Muturi, 2021).

The payment of utility bills, though relatively smaller in magnitude, shows a positive and statistically significant influence on income generation ($\beta = 0.134$, $p < 0.01$). This suggests that service diversification enhances income stability by reducing agents' dependence on a single transaction type. This result aligns with the empirical literature emphasizing income diversification as a pathway to household resilience and poverty reduction (Churchill & Marisetty, 2020). It further confirms that agency banking supports not only employment creation but also income smoothing, which is critical in volatile economic environments.

In contrast, account opening services exhibit only marginal significance ($\beta = 0.116$, $p = 0.063$). While account facilitation contributes to long-term financial deepening, its immediate income effect is limited due to relatively low commissions and infrequent demand. This finding supports earlier Nigerian studies that observed weak income effects from account opening relative to transaction-based services (Nwachukwu et al., 2019).

Regarding demographic variables, educational qualification shows a marginally significant positive effect ($\beta = 0.071$, $p = 0.071$), suggesting that higher education may slightly enhance agents' capacity to manage operations efficiently, attract customers, and diversify services. However, the modest effect indicates that agency banking remains largely inclusive and accessible, requiring limited formal education—an observation consistent with earlier conceptual discussions on employment accessibility for youths and low-skilled individuals.

Notably, gender is statistically insignificant ($\beta = 0.041$, $p = 0.261$), indicating no meaningful income disparity between male and female agency banking operators.

Figure 2: Path Coefficients for Income Generation (A diagram here visually presents the direct effects of each agency banking service and demographic factor on income generation, with the respective coefficients.)

This finding is particularly important in the context of poverty reduction, as it supports the argument advanced in the literature that agency banking offers gender-neutral income opportunities and empowers women economically (Kumar & Jie, 2023). It further reinforces the role of agency banking as an inclusive employment platform in Katsina State.

Overall, the results strongly support the study’s conceptual framework and the Financial Intermediation Theory, confirming that agency banking enhances income generation through efficient transaction delivery and localized financial intermediation.

5.1 CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of agency banking on income generation in Katsina State, Nigeria, against the backdrop of persistent unemployment, low income, and widespread poverty. Drawing on primary data analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling, the findings provide robust empirical evidence that agency banking significantly contributes to income generation among operators. The study concludes that transaction-based agency banking services particularly cash withdrawals, deposits, and transfers are the primary drivers of income generation, while service diversification through utility payments further enhances income stability. The results also demonstrate that income generation through agency banking is largely independent of gender and formal educational attainment, highlighting the inclusive nature of the model. In line with the Financial Intermediation Theory and existing empirical literature, the findings confirm that agency banking extends beyond financial access to function as a sustainable livelihood strategy, supporting self-employment, income diversification, and household welfare. In a state like Katsina, where formal employment opportunities are limited, agency banking represents a viable pathway for poverty reduction and grassroots economic empowerment.

5.2 RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

There is a need to expand agency banking networks across Katsina State, particularly in rural and underserved communities. Financial institutions and regulators should support the establishment of more

agency outlets to create additional income-generating opportunities and improve access to financial services.

Banks and fintech companies should strengthen support for high-volume transaction services such as cash withdrawals, deposits, and transfers. Improving liquidity management, transaction speed, and network reliability will help agents maximize earnings from these core services.

Agency banking operators should be encouraged to diversify their services by including utility bill payments and other value-added offerings. Such diversification can help stabilize income and reduce dependence on a single source of revenue.

Targeted capacity-building programmes should be introduced to improve agents' skills in customer service, digital operations, and basic financial management. Although formal education has limited influence, practical training can enhance efficiency and income outcomes.

Policymakers should adopt gender-inclusive policies that promote women's participation in agency banking. Access to startup capital, simplified registration procedures, and targeted support can help more women benefit from this income-generating opportunity.

Government and financial institutions should address infrastructural and security challenges affecting agency banking operations. Improvements in network connectivity, power supply, and cash security will enhance transaction volumes and income stability.

Finally, agency banking should be integrated into state and national employment and poverty-reduction strategies. Rather than being treated only as a financial inclusion tool, it should be recognized as a scalable, market-driven approach to job creation, income generation, and poverty reduction in Katsina State and Nigeria as a whole.

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